

Notas breves

Ividia havanensis (Pilsbry & Aguayo, 1933) (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Pyramidellidae) in Ascension Island

Ividia havanensis (Pilsbry & Aguayo, 1933) (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Pyramidellidae) en la isla de Ascensión

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INTRODUCTION

After the recent publication of on the Pyramidellidae of the Islands of St. Helena and Ascension (OLIVER, SWINNEN AND ROLÁN, 2023), we located an overlooked sample containing specimens of an additional species of Pyramidellidae not mentioned in the previous work. It has been identified as *Ividia havanensis* (Pilsbry & Aguayo, 1933) a widely distributed species that

we now report from the island of Ascension.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material was separated using a stereomicroscope and photographed with SEM at Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid

SYSTEMATICS

Ividia havanensis (Pilsbry & Aguayo, 1933) (Fig. 1)

Miralda havanensis (Pilsbry & Aguayo, 1933).

Original description: *Odostomia (Miralda) havanensis*: Pilsbry, H.A. & Aguayo, C.G. (1933). Marine and freshwater mollusks new to the fauna of Cuba. *The Nautilus*, 46 (4): 116-123, pl. 6, figs. 1-5, page (s): 118, pl. 6, fig. 4.

Material examined: 557 shells from 19 samples. •1 sh; Boatswain Bird Island; -27 m; 30 Avr. 2017; S. Lee leg. •4 shs; North Point reef; -7 m high density of greenalgae; 21 Aug. 2016; S. Lee leg. •31 shs; North Point; -23 m; 11 Mar. 2017; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •8 shs; Derby Wreck Reef; -9 m; 03

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Jul. 2016; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •8 shs; Derby Wreck Reef; -6.6 m; 27 Sep. 2015; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •8 shs; One Hook; 07°53'30.70"S/14°22'54.11"W; -19 m, in detritus; 14 Nov. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. •180 shs; "PamAm"; -19 m, near black coral; 18 Jul. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. •28 shs; Rocky reef between Beach and Derby Wreck; beached; 27 Sep. 2015; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •7 shs; Sudan Wreck; -14 m; 06 Aug. 2016; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •1 sh; Sudan Wreck; -14 m; 10 Oct. 2015; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •13 shs; Ladies Loo; -21 m; 21 Feb. 2016; Sarah Lee and Judith Brown leg. •37 shs; Ladies Loo; -18 m reef ledges; 12 Jun 2016; Sarah Lee & Judith Brown leg. •7 shs; Catherine Point, Arches, Georgetown; -23 m; 27 Mar. 2016; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •18 shs; below big arch, Red Rock; -12 m; Jul. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. •1 sh; Red Rock; -11 m; 28 Aug. 2016; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •18 shs; Red Rock; -22 m; 08 Oct. 2016; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •5 shs; Horse Soe Reef; -23 m; 23 Oct. 2016; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •1 sh; English Bay; -10 m, sandy seabed occasional rocky patches; 18 Jun. 2016; S. Lee and J. Brown leg. •180 shs; English Bay; -9 m, lava tunnel; 8 Feb. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg.

Type material: Academy of Natural Sciences Drexel University (ANSP Philadelphia): ANSP 159722

Type locality: La Chorrera, La Habana, Cuba.

Description: A tall, turriculate, fairly solid and white shell that in our material, with six whorls, reaches 2,0x0.9 mm.

The whorls are bicarinated. The upper cord is subsutural and the lower cord is located in the middle area of the coil. The cords are separated by concave interspaces of similar width. Both cords have regularly separated tubercles (more numerous in the lower one) that extend in the abapical direction and that narrow axially without connecting, so that no obvious axial ribs are formed. In the last round

The last whorl occupies 57% of the total height of the shell. The upper cord has fifteen tubercles while the lower one has twenty. In its basal area there are three smooth cords, separated by concave interspaces, somewhat wider. The lower cord borders the outer lip of the oral opening, oval, which reaches 35% of the height of the shell.

At high magnification, axial and longitudinal lines can be seen that, when crossed, form a reticular network more marked in the axial direction.

The protoconch is type B in which the beginning of the suture of its nucleus can be observed, in lateral vision.

Remarks: *Ivoidia havanensis* is a shallow species widely distributed along the coasts of the western Atlantic from Florida to the Brazilian coasts passing through the Caribbean Sea and the West Indies. It is represented in

numerous studies such as those of ABBOTT (1974) who cite it for Florida, ESPINOSA, ORTEA, SÁNCHEZ NODA & GUTIERREZ (2012) in Cuba, DE JONG & COOMANS (1988) in Curaçao, REDFERN (2001) in the Bahamas, DIAZ & PUYANA (1994) in the Colombian Caribbean, and Pimenta, SANTOS & ABSALÃO (2008) on the coasts of Brazil.

LANDAU & LAFOLLETTE (2015) commented that *Lia decorata* de Folin, 1873, may be a synonym of *havanensis*, or be congeneric. If true, the genus *Liamorpha* Pilsbry, 1898 (= *Lia*, de Folin 1873) would take precedence over *Ivoidia* Dall & Bartsch, 1904. However Kisch (1959) indicates that the type specimen of is reported missing from the de Folin collection at the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris. As the original drawing of *Lia decorata* is confusing, we believe that it is preferable to maintain the current generic nomenclature until the true identity of *Lia decorata* de Folin, 1873 is clarified.

In our previous work, OLIVER ET AL. (2023) indicated the presence of 8 species of Pyramidellidae on Ascension Island, so now with the incorporation of this one it increases to nine. The influence of the American Atlantic fauna in the colonization of Ascension Island is thus reinforced, as already pointed out in the previous work with species such as *Odostomella* cf. *fonteyni* (De Jong & Coomans, 1988).

Figure 1. *Ividia havanensis*. A, B: shell, 1.83×0.83 mm and protoconch; C: apical view of a protoconch; D, E: shell, 1.97×0.85 mm and protoconch; F, G: microsculpture of the teleoconch and detail.

Figura 1. Ividia havanensis. A, B: concha, $1,83 \times 0,83$ mm y protoconcha; C: vista apical de una protoconcha; D, E: concha, $1,97 \times 0,85$ y protoconcha; F, G: microescultura de la teleoconcha y detalle de la misma.

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